

**TREATMENT OPTIONS IN HYPERPLASTIC GINGIVITIS:
OZONE THERAPY UPDATES****Olesea Musteata**

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Abstract

The approach towards hyperplastic gingivitis (HG) treatment is related to the identification of the main etiological factor and the action on the site of gingival proliferation. The existing treatment modalities (conservative, surgical, physiotherapy) are not fairly efficient, recurrences often occur and existing anti-inflammatory drugs act superficially and have a temporary impact on gingiva. They are in fact limited to the elimination of the inflammatory process in the gum and the sclerosis of the hypertrophic sectors with different medication remedies (superficial and deep sclerosis) selected depending on the clinical type of hypertrophic gingivitis. A clinico-analytical, descriptive and cohort study of HG cases was realized, with a narrative review of the contemporary references concerning the subject under discussion. The researches were performed in a group of 27 patients divided into two cohorts: the control cohort 15 patients (9 females and 6 males) and the study cohort 12 patients (7 females and 5 males). The study was axed on patients included in both cohorts, diagnosed with HG using the parameters recommended by the American Academy of Periodontology (2009), aged between 17 and 68 years, with considerable increase in gingival volume up to I-III degree, false gingival pockets, glossy purplish color, bleeding on probing, supra- and subgingival dental deposits. The inclusion criteria in both cohorts enrolled patients diagnosed with HG with a lack of previous treatment for at least 3 months. The protocol for examination and treatment of patients with HG included the registration of laser Doppler flowmetry (LDF) before treatment, after treatment, then at 1 month, 3 months, 6 months, 12 months post-treatment. Subsequently, the scaling, professional brushing, air flow and sanitation of the oral cavity were performed. The average value of the blood perfusion status in the gingival tissue in the patients from the study cohort with HG evaluated based on the level of microcirculation (M) represents: until treatment 13.07; after treatment 10.71; at 1 month of treatment 11.77; at 3 months of treatment 12.27; at 6 months of treatment 12.74 and 12 months after treatment 13.26. The average value of the microcirculation efficiency index (MEI) before treatment 1.14; after treatment 1.43; at 1 month of treatment 1.46; at 3 months of treatment 1.14; at 6 months of treatment 1.21 and 12 months after treatment 1.69. Submucosal injection of medical ozone into hypertrophied papillae with a concentration of 8–10 mg/mL has been shown to be sufficient and effective in treatment. The result of the evaluation of the average value of the level of capillary blood microcirculation (M) in the hypertrophied tissue in the control cohort determined until treatment 14.60; after treatment 9.75; at 1 month of treatment 10.34; at 3 months of treatment 8.41; at 6 months of treatment 8.19 and 12 months after treatment 15.05. The result of the evaluation of the average value of the capillary blood MEI in the hypertrophied tissue in the control cohort appreciated up to treatment 0.96; after treatment 0.94; at 1 month of treatment 1.44; at 3 months of treatment 0.90; at 6 months of treatment 1.05 and 12 months after treatment 0.91. The evaluation of capillary blood microcirculation indices (M, IEM) in hypertrophied gingival tissue revealed a considerable improvement, that indicated a high response to the administered treatment. The average values of the microcirculation level (M) and of the MEI in the study cohort increased after the treatment within one month, 3, 6 and 12 months.

Keywords: hypertrophic gingivitis, microcirculation index, gingival inflammation, blood perfusion status, treatment, ozone therapy, laser Doppler flowmetry, microcirculation efficiency index.

Background: Hyperplastic gingivitis (HG) is a chronic inflammatory process, mainly located in the gingiva with the predominance of the proliferation of fibrous elements of the chorion, cellular elements and basement membrane of the gingival epithelium. Despite the diversity of etiological factors and pathogenetic mechanisms of gingival hypertrophy, the local changes emerge mainly due to the disturbance of regulation of tissue growth and the development of hyperplasia of tissue components of the gum [10]. This condition is ensured by the unfavorable action of local and general factors, may appear as a separate nosologic entity or show a symptom of other conditions and occurs without destroying the integrity of the dentogingival junction. There is usually a direct dependence between the nature of the process in the gums and the

cause of its development. HG treatment with existing traditional methods is long and difficult, post-treatment recurrences and complications often occur.

Objectives of the study: Estimation and assessment of the efficiency of the ozone administration in HG treatment with Laser Doppler flowmetry (LDF) method.

Materials and methods: A clinico-analytical, descriptive and cohort study of HG cases was performed, with a narrative review of the contemporary references related to the subject under discussion. The researches were performed in a group of 27 patients divided into two cohorts: the control group 15 patients (9 females and 6 males) and the study cohort 12 patients (7 females and 5 males). The study focused on patients included in both cohorts, diagnosed with HG using the parameters

proposed by the American Academy of Periodontology (2009), aged between 17 and 68 years, with considerable increases in gingival volume grade I–III, gingival pockets (false), glossy purplish color, bleeding on probing, supra- and subgingival dental deposits. The inclusion criteria in both groups represent patients diagnosed with HG with a lack of previous treatment of at least 3 months. The exclusion criteria were patients with hyperthyroidism, leukemia, cancer and diabetes. In the investigated cohorts, the efficiency of the administered treatment methods was comparatively evaluated: the control group (classic non-surgical conservative method in 13 patients and the classic surgical method in 2 patients) and the study group (non-surgical ozone therapy method in 12 patients). The protocol for examination and treatment of patients with HG included the registration of LDF before treatment, after treatment, then at 1 month, 3 months, 6 months, 12 months post-treatment. Subsequently, the scaling, professional brushing, air flow and sanitation of the oral cavity were performed. Submucosal injections with O₂-O₃ 8–10 mg / mL were performed every 3–4 days (from 5–10 procedures, depending on the severity of the process and recovery), intravenous perfusion or injection with O₃ in 0.09% NaCl sol., nr.10–14, 2 times a week (depending on the severity of the process and recovery). Patients in the control cohort also underwent scaling, professional brushing, superficial sclerosis of the hypertrophied gingival by instillations and swabs with cauterizing remedies and gingivectomy. Periodontal tissue probing was performed using the LAKK-02 laser-Doppler analyzer. An infrared laser provides complete information about blood flow in 1–1.5 mm of tissue. Previously, blood pressure was measured with a tonometer and pulse with a pulse oximeter. The principle of operation of the LDF method is based on the Doppler effect, where the ray of light directed towards the tissue is dispersed on its static and dynamic components [2]. Computerized analysis of LDF-graphs was performed using the program that analyzed and calculated the parameters of blood microcirculation M, σ , Kv, ALF, ACF, AHF, IEM. Where M — the microcirculation index, σ — the standard deviation of the oscillation amplitude of the blood flow, Kv — the coefficient of variation, ALF — the maximum amplitude of the oscillations of the blood flow in the low frequency band, the maximum of the high frequency oscillations of the blood flow, MEI — microcirculation efficiency index. In order to obtain stable data in the evaluation of the capillary blood microcirculation, the impression of the jaw in occlusion was obtained, then in 3 points to be examined: left, center and right, a guide tube made of copper for the Laser Doppler probe was introduced. The same procedure was repeated on the jaw. The narrative review of the references was performed under the form of a synthesis in the Discussion section of the article. In order to achieve the study objectives, the scientific publications were searched over the GoogleSearch, PubMed, Medscape, NCIB, Hinari database. More than 50 bibliographic sources were analyzed. Twelve relevant and significant primary sources were identified and selected according to the impact score

and big data, with a scientific and reproducible approach to the subject under discussion.

Results and discussions: HG is characterized by a chronic evolution. In the absence of timely administered treatment HG may lead to the serious consequences, with the formation of a wide focus of infection, mobility and tooth loss, attenuation of the body's reactivity. According to Чумакова Ю. Г. (2019), HG constitutes 24.8% of the structure of gingivitis, in pregnant women it occurs with a frequency from 8 to 24%. At the same time, the highest rate of HG disease (20.7%) is registered in the group of youngest women 18–20 years old, who usually have their first pregnancy. It is also attested in young people in the period of sexual maturity around 3–5% [7], the localized form of gingival hypertrophy represents 3–11% of all diseases of the periodontium and is mainly determined in the region of the incisors and canines of the lower and upper jaw [5]. Gingival hypertrophies are increases in the volume of the gums, of different causes. They are relatively common and produce functional and aesthetic changes [6,11,12]. The volume and color are different depending on the histological structure, most often they are bleeding, soft, inflammatory or firm and fibrous. To assess the clinical aspects of gingivitis, it is necessary to monitor the following changes in volume, shape, size, color, consistency, texture, position of the gum and blood microcirculation, ease and severity of bleeding, increased production of gingival fluid, gingival itch, pain and gingival tenderness. [3,4]. Gingival bleeding is one of the early signs of gingival inflammation and even precedes the color changes of the gingiva, being the main objective clinical sign due to micro-ulcerations in the gingival epithelium and the fragility of capillaries in the chorion [1]. Determining the degree of bleeding may be the method of evaluating regeneration processes, but limitations are described in the use of this method as a clinical parameter [5,8,10]. In order to prevent posttreatment recurrences and complications, as well as to prolong the period of HG remission, ozone therapy has been proposed, a current and modern method widely used in the practice of various medical fields. Changes in blood flow and assessment of treatment effectiveness were monitored using pre- and post-treatment LDF at 1, 3, 6, 12 months.

In our analytical studies the average value of the blood perfusion status in the gingival tissue in the patients from the study cohort with HG evaluation based on the level of microcirculation (M) constitutes: 13.07 before treatment and 10.71 after treatment; at 1 month of treatment 11.77; at 3 months of treatment 12.27; at 6 months of treatment 12.74 and 12 months after treatment 13.26. The average value of the MEI before treatment 1.14; after treatment 1.43; at 1 month of treatment 1.46; at 3 months of treatment 1.14; at 6 months of treatment 1.21 and 12 months after treatment 1.69 (Table 1 and 2). Submucosal injection of medical ozone into hypertrophied papillae with a concentration of 8–10 mg/mL has been shown to be sufficient and effective in treatment. The result of the evaluation of the average value of the level of capillary blood microcirculation (M) in the hypertrophied tissue in the control group determined until treatment 14.60; after treatment 9.75; at

1 month of treatment 10.34; at 3 months of treatment 8.41; at 6 months of treatment 8.19 and 12 months after treatment 15.05. The result of the evaluation of the average value of the capillary blood MEI in the hypertro-

phied tissue in the control group appreciated up to treatment 0.96; after treatment 0.94; at 1 month of treatment 1.44; at 3 months of treatment 0.90; at 6 months of treatment 1.05 and 12 months after treatment 0.91.

Table 1.

The result of the evaluation of the average value of the capillary blood microcirculation efficiency index (MEI) in the gingival tissue in the study cohort before treatment and within 1, 3, 6, 12 months after the treatment

Patients indicators	MEI pre	MEI post	MEI 1 month	MEI 3 months	MEI 6 months	MEI 12 months
1	0.69	0.74	0.86	0.92	1.02	1.25
2	1.00	0.95	1.14	1.23	1.34	1.40
3	0.59	0.56	0.67	0.85	0.99	1.03
4	1.07	0.77	1.34	1.41	1.53	1.56
5	0.83	0.75	0.97	1.11	1.22	1.29
6	0.94	1.56	2.00	1.21	2.02	2.05
7	1.57	0.64	1.59	1.10	1.63	1.71
8	0.96	1.41	0.91	0.91	1.57	1.64
9	1.44	0.79	0.89	1.13	1.67	1.77
10	0.9	1.79	1.33	0.85	1.43	1.51
11	1.05	1.11	2.09	1.69	1.78	1.93
12	1.14	1.43	1.46	1.14	1.47	1.66
Median value, MEI	1.015	1.041667	1.270833	1.129167	1.4725	1.566667
Standard error	0.080298	0.117897	0.130885	0.070662	0.086674	0.084273
P	<0.001					

Table 2.

The result of the evaluation of the average value of the level of capillary blood microcirculation (M) in the gingival tissue in the study cohort before treatment and within 1, 3, 6, 12 months after the treatment

Patients indicators	M pre	M post	M 1 month	M 3 months	M 6 months	M 12 months
1	11.50	12.58	10.59	12.41	13.18	11.89
2	7.67	4.36	8.14	9.03	7.09	8.60
3	14.03	7.87	11.30	11.56	13.02	13.89
4	9.36	11.32	10.51	11.33	12.14	10.90
5	10.64	9.03	10.98	11.46	9.84	10.51
6	9.62	9.51	10.34	15.05	14.52	10.62
7	16.35	11.05	8.41	8.19	11.51	14.23
8	14.6	9.75	14.79	12.74	11.02	14.2
9	15.1	10.79	13.86	17.24	16.87	15.73
10	11.92	12.45	6.98	13.26	8.18	11.79
11	10.85	4.53	16.27	7.18	13.74	13.19
12	13.07	10.71	11.77	12.27	12.78	12.61
Median value, M indicator	12.05917	9.495833	11.16167	11.81	11.99083	12.34667
Median error	0.755423	0.783798	0.790944	0.808134	0.782001	0.581239
P	<0.1					

Conclusions:

1. The evaluation of capillary blood microcirculation indices (M, IEM) in hypertrophied gingival tissue revealed a considerable improvement, which indicated a high response to the administered treatment.

2. The average values of the microcirculation level (M) and of MEI in the study cohort increased within 1 month, 3 months, 6 months and 12 months after the treatment.

3. Submucosal injection of medical ozone into hypertrophied papillae with a concentration of 8–10 mg/mL may be considered as an effective and sufficient treatment option.

4. No statistically significant positive changes of M and MEI were registered in the control cohort, in which their unstable and minor growth was revealed.

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